

SHORT NOTES

Oxo-vanadium (IV) Complexes

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In continuation with our previous work on vanadium complexes¹⁻³ another group of complexes of the type $[\text{VOR}_2]$ (where R = a molecule of acetoacetanilide, acetoacetylaldehyde, acetoacetanilide or acetoacet *o*-chloroanilide) has now been characterised. The acetoacetylaldehyde complexes appear to be less stable than those of the β -diketones and do not seem to furnish easily the six-co-ordinated adducts. The closely related kojic acid has also produced a similar complex. These are all bluish-green to green in colour and provide normal magnetic moments (1.6–1.8 B.M.),

Salicylamidoxime⁴ (RH) reacts with VO^{2+} , producing an ash-coloured paramagnetic $[\text{VOR}_2]$ which easily oxidises to greenish black diamagnetic $[(\text{VO}(\text{OH})\text{R}_2)]_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The latter complex yields alkoxo complexes with alcohols.

α -Nitroso- β -naphthol (RH) reacts with vanadium (IV) providing cinnamon-black $[\text{VOR}_2]$ (paramagnetic) and with vanadium (V), a dark red $[\text{VO}_2\text{R}]$ (diamagnetic). Reactions of β -nitroso- α -naphthol are comparable.

Further to our studies on the heterochelates¹⁻³ of oxo-vanadium(IV) having one tridentate dibasic or tribasic acid, such as pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid, 4-hydroxy-pyridine 2, 6-dicarboxylic acid or 2, 4, 6, -tricarboxylic acid, we have now succeeded in synthesising a new series of heterochelates containing the bidentate oxalate radical and one of *o*-phenanthroline, α - α' -dipyridyl, oxin, picolinic acid, 2-guanidinobenzimidazole etc. The heterochelates have been obtained in pure, crystalline form by the action of the bidentate ligands on vanadyl oxalate $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]$ obtained *in situ* by the reaction of one mole of V_2O_5 with 3 moles of oxalic acid. These are green to blue in colour and are paramagnetic. The equivalent weights, conductances, and the dissociation constants of some of these heterochelates have also been evaluated. A few representative complexes are included in Table I.

1. Dutta and Labry, *this Journal*, 1961, **38**, 1001; 1962, **39**, 871; 660; 1963, **40**, 53, 67, 857; 1964, **41**, 62, 549; *Chem & Ind.*, 1961, 78.
2. Dutta, *et al*, *Science & Culture*, 1964, **30**, 351.
3. Dutta and Ghosh, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.* 1966, **1**,
4. Bandyopadhyay & Ray, *this Journal*. 1966, **33**, 21
5. Selbin & Holmes, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.* 1962, **24**, 1116.

TABLE I

Complex	Colour	
1. Oxo-bis-(acetacetanilide) vanadium(IV)	Light bluish green	Found: V, 12.4; N, 6.91% Reqd: V, 12.1; N, 6.92%
2. Oxo-bis-(salicylamidoxime)vanadium(IV)	Ash	Found: V, 13.6; N, 15.0% Reqd: V, 13.8; N, 15.1%
3. Oxo-hydroxo-bis-(salicylamidoxime) vanadium (V) dihydrate	greenish-black	Found: V, 12.20; N, 13.30; H ₂ O, 8.0 Reqd: V, 12.1; N, 13.27; H ₂ O, 8.6
4. Oxo-bis-(α -nitroso- β -naphthol) vanadium (IV)	Cinnamon black	Found: V, 12.7; N, 7.0 Reqd: V, 12.4; N, 6.8
5. Dioxo-(α -nitroso- β -naphthol) vanadium (V)	Dark red	Found: V, 19.9; N, 5.70% Reqd: V, 20.0; N, 5.49%
*6. Oxo-(<i>o</i> -phenanthroline) oxalato vanadium (IV)	Leaf-green	Found: V, 15.19; N, 8.41% Reqd: V, 15.23; N, 8.36%
7. Oxo-oxinato-oxalato-vanadium(IV) acid	Bluish green	Found: V, 18.78; N, 4.52% Reqd: V, 17.00; N, 4.56%
8. Oxo-picolinato-oxalato vanadium (IV) acid monohydrate	green	Found: V, 17.22; N, 4.55; H ₂ O, 6.13% Reqd: V, 17.23; N, 4.73; H ₂ O, 6.10%

*This compound has been reported previously in a state of lower purity by a different procedure.⁵

Studies on the visible and IR spectra as also on the thermal dissociation of these complexes are progressing and details will be reported later.

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